

WOMEN IN STEM IN HIGH EDUCATION IN LATIN AMERICA

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POLICY STATEMENT

Latin America and the Caribbean have already held at least 12 regional (1) conferences on women (2). This region stands out from other regions of the world in producing political and technical agreements that demonstrate the commitment of governments. Despite their ups and downs, these commitments have uniquely contributed to the path of Latin American and Caribbean societies towards achieving equality between women and men. The regional agreements were also characterized by the organization of a broad international agenda at the turn of the century, which led to the Beijing Platform for Action and the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) established at the Millennium Summit (2000), which is now marked by the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, adopted by the UN in 2015.

As highlighted in Sustainable Development Goal 5, gender equality is not only a fundamental human right, but also the necessary foundation for a peaceful, prosperous and sustainable world. The role of governments, civil society - especially women's organizations - international human rights heads have been the key to build a regional gender agenda that recognizes women's rights and equality as essential and transversal elements of action. The government's responsibility to reduce gender disparities. Science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) education has an essential role to play in this transformation as it supports the 2030 Agenda.

BACKGROUND

Advances in STEM areas have already brought improvements in many aspects of human life, such as health, agriculture, infrastructure and renewable energy (3). STEM education is also one of the keys to preparing students, especially women, for the world of work and scientific production. At the moment, despite the improvement in indicators, women still remain underrepresented in STEM in universities in Latin America. There are many transversal factors that need to be constantly analyzed, such as the fatal representation of women in STEM, depending on race and ethnicity.

The public policies in the countries, especially Latin American countries, have not highlighted many obstacles to the empowerment of women in STEM. The lack of opportunities given to women in decision-making spaces is another issue that should be addressed. As an example, only 10% of women were members of the World Academy of Sciences, while 14% of women were members of Latin America's Academy of Sciences. In contrast, we found a greater abandonment of STEM subjects by women than men at the undergraduate level (4).

FINDINGS

The gender disparity in STEM in Latin America also widens in the transition from undergraduate to graduate studies, and in post-doctoral studies the highest dropout rate is among women, even though they have invested so much time in studying. The hypothesis we highlight is that university policies are insufficient to prevent women from leaving STEM because of discrimination and harassment in male-dominated environments. However, there is also the argument that there is a low success rate in university policies for giving opportunities to women in science. This is primarily because it is difficult to find educational programs that address the gender issue and promote change in STEM. From graduation to the empowerment of women scientists in STEM, there is a basic problem, that is, low assimilation of institutional policies for this type of career in Latin America.

CONCLUSIONS

We understand that actions must take into account the governmental support policies for women in regional and sub-regional STEM in each country in Latin America. It is from Higher Education and all gender equality policies that we can understand why gender disparities are more evident in STEM. Policies in Higher Education Institutions in Latin America are not enough to promote gender equality in STEM fields. This is because there is a lack of educational programs, sensitive to the issue of gender, that help to raise awareness and promote changes in STEM.

Another problem that affects women is the lack of time, reflected in the negative indicators, which leads us to a brief, more careful description of this situation. To emphasize unwaged work, which mainly involves women, SDG 5 (achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls) is very relevant. Despite the social changes that have taken place over the centuries (increased participation of women in the labor market, increasing schooling, reduced fertility, dissemination of contraceptive methods, and access to information), women continue to dedicate more time to household chores and care than men. Most women need to combine paid work with housework and care, and in many cases they end up working in occupations with reduced hours. We observe that the scarcity of time in women's lives harms them in caring for their own health. This is another obstacle to building a professional trajectory and personal fulfillment.

RECOMMENDATIONS

There is a line of research that helps us think about the problem of the gender gap in STEM education and that is true not only in Latin America, but all over the world, and that there is discrimination and gender stereotypes coming up from the primary education level (lack of family support, teachers

unprepared to deal with gender issues, and social environment that influences girls' career decisions), to the higher education level (lack of motivation to invest in STEM, whether it is due to sexual harassment or any other form of discrimination). Another sensitive aspect that should be mentioned has to do with women's sexual and reproductive rights. It is on women that the responsibility for the care of children falls and, therefore, motherhood has a stronger, and often negative, effect on economic opportunities and leadership in decision-making positions.

REFERENCES

- (1) In Latin America and the Caribbean, the construction of the women's rights agenda in international organizations began in 1928, in Havana. This was when women came together to demand their participation in the Sixth International American Conference and the ratification of the Treaty on Equal Rights. From there, the Inter-American Commission on Women (CIM) was created. In force today, the CIM is the first intergovernmental body in the world created expressly with the aim of ensuring the recognition of women's civil and political rights. Available: ww.oas.org/es/cim/
- (2) All agreements emanating from the 12 meetings of the Regional Conference on Women in Latin America and the Caribbean mentioned in this document can be found in ECLAC (2016c) and in the biblioguide that allows a detailed search of articles and agreements. Available [on-line] <http://biblioguias.cepal.org/AgendaRegionalGenero>
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